

STUDY OF SAMPLES OF CLAY MINERALS OBTAINED IN NAVOI AND SAMARKAND REGIONS

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There are 118 bentonite and 25 kaolin-containing clays in the Navoi and Samarkand regions, among which 38 bentonite and 10 kaolin samples are currently being used and considered suitable for use[1]. We conducted a study of clays as objects in the Navoi region – Altintov and Zaqquduq, and in the Samarqand region – Alyans and Qarnob. The chemical analysis of these selected clays using the titrimetric method is presented in the following Table 1.

Table 1

№	Place names	Chemical composition												
		Al ₂ O ₃	SiO ₂	TiO ₂	Fe ₂ O ₃	FeO	MnO	CaO	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	P ₂ O ₅	SO ₃	ch. y.
1.	Altintov	26,31	54,01	0,340	0,88	0,29	0,01	4,21	0,50	1,52	0,29	0,084	0,21	12,06
2.	Zaqquduq	34,56	46,11	1,160	0,54	0,25	0,01	1,68	1,11	1,53	0,12	0,063	0,84	13,00
3.	Qarnob	18,17	62,04	0,870	3,49	0,25	0,01	1,12	1,11	2,03	3,53	0,110	0,50	7,44
4.	Alyans	18,28	56,55	0,24	0,26	-	0,01	3,78	0,40	0,12	0,56	0,071	4,33	15,35
5.	Alyans 2	21,83	66,73	0,33	0,37	-	0,01	1,12	0,50	0,22	0,52	0,083	1,10	7,82

From the table, it can be seen that the clay samples of Altintov, Zaqquduq, and Alyans can be distinguished based on the amount of clay in their composition. Considering the high content of clay and the low content of ferrous oxides in their composition, it is necessary to consider Zaqquduq clay as refractory, while Altintov and Alyans clays are considered suitable for producing delicate ceramic samples. Using Qarnob clay is essential as a valuable raw material for manufacturing ceramic materials.

The geological occurrence of these clays differs from one another according to their natural emergence:

1. Altintov primary kaolins are found in hydroslyuda and kaolin zones, secondary kaolins are located together with clay inclusions (with a thickness of 5-10 m) in direct conjunction with primary kaolins.

2. Zaqquduq kaolin-containing clays are the result of the weathering of granite rocks, and a significant degree of radiation has been detected in the composition of primary kaolins.

3. Alyans clay is the result of the weathering of granitic-gneiss masses of the Ketmenchi range.

Based on the mineralogical composition, these clays differ as follows:

1. Altintov clay sample contains minerals such as kaolinite, quartz, mica, clay, and nontronite.

2. Zaqquduq clay contains minerals such as kaolinite, sericite, quartz, feldspar, andesite, rutile, pyrite, and getite.

3. Alyans clay contains kaolinite, quartz, feldspar, and clay.

Qarnob clay enters the group of polymetallic clays, and its composition includes kaolinite, quartz, feldspar, muscovite, sericite, biotite, rutile minerals.

Clay particles with a size of 0.2-0.4 microns, kaolins marked as KVF-90-1, are used for the production of ceramic refractories[2].

Kaolin is considered a dispersant in plastics and composite materials. Its characteristic is generally attributed to the absence of brittleness, low humidity, and high resistance to heat. When used, it provides flexibility, impermeability, and high durability to polymer materials.

Advantages of using kaolin in the production of plastics:

- high flexibility upon bending;
- good electrical properties;
- high electrical resistance;
- higher bonding parameters compared to reinforced fiberglass based on polyester resins;
- lower water absorption properties;
- slows down the aging process of polymer materials[3].

When kaolin is reprocessed with organic acid solutions (such as acetic acid or its mixtures), it is found to significantly decrease crystalline lattice compared to inorganic acids. When kaolin is reprocessed with acetic acid and subsequently

treated with sodium hydroxide solution, the volume of absorbable open cavities increased by 1.5 times.

When kaolin is reprocessed in a biologically active environment (in vinegar, olive, or sunflower oil) with phosphates, heavy metal cations in an acidic environment, their sorption properties together increase[4].

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